

What is a campaign?

A campaign is a data gathering event to gather pollution data in a specific and/or sparse area and within a time window. Thus, a campaign is a pre-defined period in which air pollution measurements take place. A campaign can vary in length, ranging from an afternoon to a month. For longer measurement requirements we propose to consider this to be a new campaign, for users to be able to disengage if they want to. Longer campaigns might lead to erosion in participation levels.

Citizens can participate by making use of SOCIO-BEE wearable sensors (even a drone) and a mobile app. Hence, those willing to participate in the data gathering and consequent data analysis are able to crowdsource air quality data. Using the hive analogy of SOCIO-BEE, the people will mimic what Working Bees (WB) do in the hives with the pollen.

The campaigns are set by Beekeepers and QueenBees (QBs). They are responsible for the campaigns' definition, publication, monitoring, and staffing. They will define one or more different campaign types (based on predefined blueprints) with different associated measurement-gathering strategies based on the objective of each campaign type. They may also include types of analysis and algorithms that may be used to analyze data in order to test a hypothesis through a Citizen Science-based experiment. In general, there are two types of campaigns: 1) type I area investigation – based on explore an area, 2) type II source investigation – based on examining a pollution source.

Campaign templates (blueprints) will be made available for Beekeepers and used by QBs when they are creating a new campaign in order to provide them with some ideas, materials, or guides to start with.

What is a Citizen Science-based experiment in SOCIO-BEE?

It is based on the definition of a scientific hypothesis that should be validated or tested wrong by the execution of a campaign(s) involving civil society and the consequent collective analysis of the data gathered.

The results of such experiments should be disseminated by Drone Bees (DB) to enhance awareness about air quality pollution among citizens and foster possible mitigation actions by relevant actors with decision power (Bears).

In essence, an experiment can be made up of one or more campaigns. It serves the purpose of testing one hypothesis. Campaigns are run by hives, i.e. a hive has to be assembled before a campaign is launched.

What is a Hypothesis?

A hypothesis (plural: hypotheses), in a scientific context, is a testable statement about the relationship between two or more variables or a proposed explanation for some observed phenomenon.

It is the initial building block of the scientific method. Many describe it as an "educated guess" based on prior knowledge and observation. While this is true, a hypothesis is more informed than a guess. While an "educated guess" suggests a random prediction based on a person's expertise, developing a hypothesis requires active observation and background research.

The basic idea of a hypothesis is that there is no predetermined outcome. For a solution to be termed a scientific hypothesis, it has to be an idea that can be supported or refuted through carefully crafted experimentation or observation. This concept is called falsifiability and testability (it should be possible to prove it wrong). A key function of a hypothesis is to derive predictions about the results of future experiments and then perform those experiments to see whether they support the predictions.

How to set a "what if scenario" or a hypothesis?

A hypothesis is usually written in the form of an if-then statement, which gives a possibility (if) and explains what may happen because of the possibility (then). The statement could also include "may". For example, "If I do not submit deliverables, then I may fail the evaluation from the EU reviewers." The "if" and "then" statements reflect your independent and dependent variables.

Other examples based on Air Quality (AQ):

- "If trees absorb CO₂, then a neighborhood that is given with trees may have cleaner air".
- "If PM_{2.5} causes breath injuries such as shortness of breath, then people who live in areas with a high concentration of PM_{2.5} may be more prone to these diseases".
- "If O₃ can create asthma attacks, then maybe this Ozone can be responsible for the increase in hospital admissions (overall among children)".

Other options are exploring ideas:

- We expect the pollution to be higher at the crossroads than in the park
- We expect the pollution measurements to be higher on a warm, calm day than on a cool, windy day
- We expect the trees next to the road to have a diminishing effect on pollution

What not to do!

An example of an untestable statement is, "Dogs are better than cats." That's because the definition of "better" is vague and subjective. However, an untestable statement can be reworded to make it testable. For example, the previous statement could be changed to this: "Owning a dog is associated with higher levels of physical fitness than owning a cat." With this statement, the researcher can take measures of physical fitness from dog and cat owners and compare the two.

Types of Scenarios contemplated in SOCIO-BEE

During the initial ideation phase, 9 types of Scenarios were proposed by SOCIO-BEE partners. The scenarios which are more prone to be tested are Scenarios 2, 4, 6, and 9.

scenario 1

drone including sensor
must not exceed
250 gram!!

scenario 3

drone category C+

with formal 'go' drones can
fly over urban areas

scenario 5

Stationary sensors in the
balcony

scenario 7

Using stationary sensors in
public spaces

scenario 2

drone category C1
< 25000 gram

scenario 4

plan B: Kites as low
tech alternative

scenario 6

Walking routes sensing at
nose level

scenario 8

Using wearable sensors
attached to vehicles

scenario 9

Letting citizens build and
experiment with sensors –
DIY approach

Types of CS Experiments

In the following Figure, we propose some ideas on top of each scenario presented above. As can be seen, these ideas are related to WHAT to explore (AQ) and WHEN (time frame). However, more concrete ideas for campaigns are described below in the following Section (Blueprints).

What is a campaign blueprint?

Campaign blueprints are templates of potential campaigns to be run in the context of the SOCIO-BEE project.

They can be consulted by Beekeepers and QBs to select the one(s) which is/are more convenient to prove the hypothesis raised collectively by the hive.

The campaign's blueprint will help bees to address questions related to HOW, WHAT, and WHEN making measurements (aka, do pollen gathering and pollination activities).

The campaign blueprints are tightly coupled with the wearable sensor developed in the context of the project, but they can be reused/applied in other contexts beyond SOCIO-BEE (e.g., citizens aiming to explore their environments with other low-cost sensors).

Some of the blueprints conceived so far are:

Campaign Blueprint 1: Pollinate a specific area in a short period of time. (type I)

Time: one to three hours.

Sensors: Bring back the wearable to the place where the campaign started.

A Hive identifies a particular area that needs to be investigated/captured to test a hypothesis. The bees will be able to see a map with information related to what cells in that area have been already covered by bee-mates and which still have to be covered. The areas will use color coding to depict this information. The aim of the campaign is to cover the entire area to create a map as soon as possible. It needs several measurements per cell in the given time and it would be advisable to have a similar number of measurements in each cell. This type of campaign blueprint is good for you if: (1) the number of bees is low; (2) the availability of end-users is low; (3) if they can commit to hard work over a short period of time.

Example: A campaign that runs in an area with a hot summer and not a lot of wind will result in different outcomes when repeated in wintertime under more windy conditions (smog vs no smog risk).

Identified needs to set the campaign (QB):

- The campaign duration
 - The time period to accomplish the campaign (e.g., three hours).
 - Start time and end time
 - Measured in hours.
 - Valid Working period of the campaign (e.g., from 8 am to 9 pm)
 - The time-division of the campaigns into slots (measured in time) - Aim: **important not to assign someone to take measurements overnight.**
 - **Null** (the campaign is very short to be divided into slots)
- Total area to cover.
 - Number of areas:
 - 1 to 100
 - Always a center in GPS coordinates has to be provided.
 - Latitude and longitude
 - The QB should select the radius in meters with a slider. For this blueprint:
 - **Not more than a Km of distance.**
- The cells' distance to cover the whole area. It will give the number of cells to be pollinated for the given area (see Figure below).
 - Three options will be offered:
 - sparse,
 - **good fit,**

- condensed.
- The number of measurements per cell per slot to flag it as pollinated.
 - **Null (the more, the merrier)**
- The minimum number of bees needed to start the campaign.
 - Number of bees: **2**
 - The campaign can only start when this number is reached.

Campaign Blueprint 2: Pollinate an area over a longer period of time (type I)

Time: 1 day to 1 month.

Sensor: Take the sensor home and bring it back when the campaign finishes.

Either Beekeeper or Queen Bee identifies a particular area that needs to be investigated/captured, but with an additional ambition to cover it over time. That is, this campaign aims at investigating an area for longer to make time-series comparisons.

In this campaign, AQ in cells associated with the area should be captured in the morning, afternoon, and evening, for example. This campaign will define daily time slots to be reset when the minimum number of samples to be gathered in each slot is reached or when the timeslot finishes. The bees will be able to see what cells in that area have been covered in each time slot as in campaign blueprint 1. Moreover, they will be able to see the differences in measurements per time slot.

Example: A campaign wants to measure the impact of traffic. The particular source, a busy junction, is susceptible to rush hour peaks. The Hive should consider measuring before, during and after rush hour.

Identified needs to set the campaign (QB):

- The campaign duration
 - The time period to accomplish the campaign (e.g., one week).
 - Start time and end time
 - Measured in hours.
 - Valid Working period of the campaign
 - The time-division of the campaigns into slots (measured in time) - Aim: **important not to assign someone to take measurements overnight.**
 - From 8 am to 8 pm
- Total area to cover.
 - Number of areas:
 - 1 to 100
 - Always a center in GPS coordinates has to be provided.
 - Latitude and longitude
 - The QB should select the radius in meters with a slider. For this blueprint:
 - **Not more than a Km of distance.**
- The cells' distance to cover the whole area. It will give the number of cells to be pollinated for the given area (see Figure below).
 - Three options will be offered:
 - **sparse,**
 - good fit,
 - condensed.
- The number of measurements per cell per slot to flag it as pollinated.
 - **Five (the more, the merrier)**
- The minimum number of bees needed to start the campaign.
 - Number of bees: **2**

Figure 1. Slot 1 (e.g., morning)

Figure 2. Slot 2 (e.g., noon)

Figure 3. Slot 3 (e.g., afternoon)

Figure 4. Slot 4 (e.g., evening)

Campaign Blueprint 3: Pollinize an area around a source of pollution over a short period of time (type II)

Time: 1 hour to 5 hours.

Sensor: Take the sensor home and bring it back when the campaign finishes.

Drones: Nice fit

Either a Beekeeper or Queen Bee identifies a particular target that needs to be investigated further (e.g., a hot spot such a place where many traffic jams occur or a black point such as coal plant/factory).

Other examples of sources of pollution:

- a source can be a road with intensive polluting traffic using combustion engines.
- a source can be a hot spot with a lot of waiting for traffic with combustion engines like a crossroad
- with traffic lights.
- a source can be a temporary source like a building site, a festival, a football match in the local stadium, or another event-like occurrence.
- a source can be a continuous source of emissions like a factory or a plant
- a source can be house-based sources (chimney bearing houses) emitting fireplace/wood
- burning, oil, petrol or coal-based emissions.

A second source to be explored is clean hotspots like parks, forests, meadows, or green zones, but on closer scrutiny can still suffer from pollution effects despite their appearance at first glance. A final source is the Pollution reduction sources like are groupings of trees or shrubbery near other sources (like roads or factories) that are prone to reduce air pollution density.

The bees will have to cover the area around the source expanding the measurement in concentric circles throughout the time to then analyze how pollution spreads (e.g., pesticides and other chemicals have been found in the Antarctic ice sheet. In the middle of the northern Pacific Ocean, a huge collection of microscopic plastic particles forms what is known as the Great Pacific Garbage Patch.). In a micro scale, it may serve to understand how pollution spreads around neighborhoods.

the campaign will start on the smallest area and then expand to the next bigger one until the spreading area is fully covered. In each slot of time, only cells in specific ring areas will be promoted/suggested.

Identified needs to set the campaign (QB):

- The campaign duration
 - The time period to accomplish the campaign (e.g., 4 hours).
 - Start time and end time
 - Measured in hours.
 - Valid Working period of the campaign
 - The time-division of the campaigns into slots (measured in time) - Aim: **important not to assign someone to take measurements overnight.**
 - **Null** (The more measurements per cell, the merrier)
- Total area to cover.
 - Number of areas:
 - 1
 - Always a center in GPS coordinates has to be provided.
 - Latitude and longitude
 - The QB should select the radius in meters with a slider. For this blueprint:
 - 1st ring: No more than 50 m.
 - 2nd ring: No more than 200 m
 - 3rd ring: No more than 500 m.
 - 4th ring: No more than 1 km

- The cells' distance to cover the whole area. It will give the number of cells to be pollinated for the given area (see Figure below).
 - Three options will be offered:
 - sparse,
 - good fit,
 - **condensed.**
- The number of measurements per cell per slot to flag it as pollinated.
 - **Null (the more, the merrier)**
- The minimum number of bees needed to start the campaign.
 - Number of bees: **10**

Campaign Blueprint 4: Pollinize an area around a source of pollution over a longer period of time (type II)

Time: 1 day to 1 month.

Sensors: Bring back the wearable to the place where the campaign started.

Drones: Nice fit

Exactly the same campaign as Campaign Blueprint 3, but with a longer time period to examine better the influence of the pollution sparsity taking into account the slots throughout each of the days the campaign will be active (i.e., a mix of campaigns 2 and 3). This campaign is interesting as the amount of traffic or the gas emissions from plants can be higher or lower depending on the hour of the day.

Identified needs to set the campaign (QB):

- The campaign duration
 - The time period to accomplish the campaign (e.g., 3 weeks).
 - Start time and end time
 - Measured in hours.
 - Valid Working period of the campaign
 - The time-division of the campaigns into slots (measured in time)
 - The whole day as pollution also matters overnight
- Total area to cover.
 - Number of areas:
 - 1
 - Always a center in GPS coordinates has to be provided.
 - Latitude and longitude
 - The QB should select the radius in meters with a slider. For this blueprint:
 - 1st ring: No more than 50 m.
 - 2nd ring: No more than 200 m
 - 3rd ring: No more than 500 m.
 - 4th ring: No more than 1 km
- The cells' distance to cover the whole area. It will give the number of cells to be pollinated for the given area (see Figure below).
 - Three options will be offered:
 - sparse,
 - **good fit,**
 - condensed.
- The number of measurements per cell per slot to flag it as pollinated.
 - **5 (the more, the merrier)**
- The minimum number of bees needed to start the campaign.
 - Number of bees: **10**

Figure 1. Slot 1 (e.g., morning)

Figure 2. Slot 2 (e.g., noon)

Figure 3. Slot 3 (e.g., afternoon)

Figure 4. Slot 4 (e.g., evening)

Source of truth: assign as epicenter a physical air quality station

All devices in the same spot: do all get the same/equivalent values? Data quality

Confounding variables:

Some environmental variables a Hive should consider that will influence the measurement campaigns while running are:

- Sunshine can cause some pollutants to undergo chemical reactions, resulting in the development of smog
- Higher air temperatures can speed up chemical reactions in the air
- Rain typically results in less pollution since it washes away the particulate matter and can also wash out pollutants that are dissolvable
- Wind speed, air turbulence, and mixing depth all affect how pollutants disperse or spread out from an area

Campaign template to create new blueprints or have new ideas for hypothesis testing

Stakeholders - WHO	<p>Who will be actively taking part as queen bees or worker bees the campaign?</p> <p>Who will play the role of Bear and Beekeeper in your campaign?</p> <p>Who will play the role of Drones, helping you disseminate the outcomes of the campaign?</p>
Goal - WHAT	<p>What is aimed at your pilot in the context of this campaign?</p> <p>List the objectives that will be followed in this campaign</p> <p>Formulate the scientific hypothesis you want to prove.</p>
Workplan - WHEN	<p>What are the phases, tasks, and milestones to be tackled?</p> <p>List the activities that you will carry out to ensure that the campaign is executed in time and form. Take into account the four phases:</p> <p>Anticipate and list any potential risks and possible mitigation actions to execute this campaign in the assigned period. Propose workarounds if needed.</p>

Location - WHERE	Where in the city you will be taking measurements for this campaign?
Materials & equipment - WHICH	List your assumptions regarding infrastructure, number of sensors, and expected date for availability What functionalities should SOCIO-BEE tools provide to Beekeepers, Queen Bees, and Worker Bees taking part in the campaign?
Methodology - HOW	What strategy will you use to pollinate cells in a campaign's surface (e.g. pollinate an area over a time period)? What data variables should be gathered in the crowdsourcing produced by the hive? What algorithms and analytical methods will you apply to process measurements? What visualization and KPIs do you want to calculate to support decision-making around AQ?

**Reasoning - WHY
(outcomes)**

Purpose of the campaign. Why is this campaign necessary?

Who will benefit from this campaign?

What will the outcomes of this campaign be used for?

The possible impact expected from this campaign

UX - Front-end campaigns

Working bees in the hive have to decide:

- If they join or not campaigns.
- If they sign in in a given campaign:
 - Register and activate (make available) their device (ready to make measurements).
 - Receive notifications:
 - Set up if they want to be notified: **Yes/No**
 - Define when they are available to receive gathering notifications in this campaign. (slots of time to pollinate per week: calendar availability)
 - *Define the number of notifications per day OR the maximum number of measurements per day to gather.*

Queen Bees can:

- See the status of the campaign
- Send notifications to working bees in the campaign: *Cheer up! We can do it! Thanks for your contribution!*
- Take measurements as if they were WBs (automatically)